

Reactions of Thioureas. Part I. Some Diphenyl Sulphides from Thiourea and Polynitrohalogeno-benzenes

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Thiourea, when refluxed with halogeno-polynitrobenzenes in ethanolic solution in presence of sodium acetate, provides polynitrodiphenyl sulphides. Diphenyl sulphides obtained from a few polynitrohalogenobenzenes are described.

The reaction of thiourea with alkyl halides, affording the corresponding stable thiuronium halides, is well known¹. Its behaviour with polynitrohalogeno-benzenes with reactive halogen atoms, which can be expected to be similar, has, however, been little investigated. Taylor and Dixon² found that when 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene and picryl chloride reacted with thiourea, unstable thiuronium chlorides were first formed; the final product, however, depended on the solvent, temperature, and nature of the nitrohalogeno-benzene. A systematic study of the reaction has been carried out. It has been found that when thiourea, 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene, sodium acetate, and ethanol are refluxed, 2,2',4,4'-tetranitrodiphenyl sulphide is formed in fairly good yield. Under similar conditions 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-(I), 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-(II), 1,2,3-trichloro-4,6-dinitro-(III), 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-3-methyl-(IV), 1-chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-(V), 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitro-(VI), 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-(VII), 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-(VIII), and 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-(IX) benzene furnish 3,3'-dichloro-4,4',6,6'-tetranitro-(A), 4,4'-dichloro-2,2',6,6'-tetranitro-(B), 2,2',3,3'-tetrachloro-4,4',6,6'-tetranitro-(C), 2,2',4,4',6,6'-hexanitro-3,3'-dimethyl-(D), 4,4',6,6'-tetranitro-3,3'-dimethyl-(E), 2,2',5,5'-tetrachloro-4,4',6,6'-tetranitro-(F), 3,3'-dichloro-4,4',6,6'-tetranitro-2,2'-dimethyl-(G), 2,2'-dichloro-4,4',6,6'-tetranitro-5,5'-dimethyl-(H), and 2,2',4,4',6,6'-hexanitro-(I) diphenyl sulphide respectively.

The diphenyl sulphides are coloured crystalline compounds, sparingly soluble in ethanol and acetic acid but easily dissolve in acetone. The yield of the products was found to be comparatively low from halogeno-nitrobenzenes having two bulky groups in both the *ortho* positions to the reactive halogen atoms.

Of the polynitrohalogeno-benzenes, 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene, which has two reactive halogen atoms (in 1- and 3-positions), can form two isomeric diphenyl sulphides; only one compound, however, could be isolated. As it is identical with the compound obtained from 3-bromo-1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene, it must be 2,2',5,5'-tetrachloro-4,4',6,6'-tetranitrodiphenyl sulphide.

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1. Bernthsen *et al*, *Ber.*, 1878, 11, 493; 1879, 12, 575; Wheeler, *Amer. Chem. J.* 1903, 29, 482; 1905, 33, 440; Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 285.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 243.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedure.—1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (4.04 g., 0.02M) and thiourea (0.76 g., 0.01M) were dissolved in 95% ethanol (25 ml) and sodium acetate (2.0 g.) was added to the solution. The mixture was refluxed for about 1 hour on a water bath, when a crystalline compound separated. It was filtered at the pump and washed with a little water. On crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, 2,2',4,4'-tetranitrodiphenyl sulphide was obtained in yellow crystals (3.0 g.), m.p. 195°. (Found: S, 8.52. $C_{12}H_6O_8N_4S$ requires S, 8.74%). The compound was found identical with an authentic specimen³.

Following the above procedure, nine other polynitrohalogeno-benzenes (I to IX), having a reactive halogen, were converted into the respective diphenyl sulphides (A to I), described in Table I.

TABLE I

Polynitro halogeno- benzene.	Diphenyl sulphide formed.	Yield.	Colour.	M.P.	Solvent for reflux.	Time of reflux.	% Sulphur.	
							Found.	Reqd.
I	A	75%	Light orange	220°(d)	EtOH	1 hr.	7.20	7.33
II	B	25	Light brown	174°	PrOH ^a	6	7.15	7.33
III	C	40	Yellow	280°(d)	EtOH	2	6.23	6.34
IV	D	15	Dark grey	170°	„	6	6.39	6.61
V	E	65	Greenish yellow	185°	„	1	8.03	8.12
VI	F	20	Reddish brown	175°	PrOH ^a	18	6.17	6.34
VII	G	25	Yellowish orange	178°	EtOH	6	6.60	6.91
VIII	H	30	Light brown	182°	PrOH ^a	18	6.74	6.91
IX	I	30	Red	184°	EtOH (absolute)	8	6.89	7.00

N.B. (d) denotes decomposition.

Authors' sincere thanks are due to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra, Head of the Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, for providing facilities in his department.